

Reaction of eight rices to gall midge (GM)

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CO 37 (Vaigai), IR50, ACM2, ACM8, ACM9, ACM10, ARC10550, and TN1 were field tested for resistance to GM during the first growing season. Seedlings were transplanted at 30 d in 2- × 1.5-m plots in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Silvershoot damage on 5 randomly selected hills was recorded at 30 and 50 days after

Response of 8 rice varieties to GM in Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Source	Maturity (d)	Silvershoot damage ^a (%)		Yield (t/ha)
			30 DT	50 DT	
ACM8	IR8/W1263	120	3.6 a	2.8 a	4.8
ARC10550	Selection from Vellutha Cheera	125	5.1 a	7.0 b	2.4
TN1	DG WG/Tsai-Yan-Chung	135	17.2 b	17.8 cd	3.6
IR50	IR2153-14-1-62/IR28//IR2070-625-1	105	21.9 bc	21.2 cd	5.4
CO 37 (Vaigai)	TN1/CO 29	120	21.9 bc	33.2 e	5.1
ACM9	IET7281	110	22.3 bc	17.1 c	4.8
ACM10	IRCTN 09546	115	24.6 c	24.4 d	6.3
ACM2	Kannagi/IR28	105	27.3 c	27.5 e	4.2

^a Mean of 15 plants. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

planting (DT).

GM damage at 30 DT ranged from 3.6% on ACM8 to 27.3% on ACM2

(see table). At 50 DT, the range was from 2.8% on ACM8 to 33.2% on CO 37. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OTHER PESTS

Resistance of some rice varieties to the root-knot nematode (RKN) *Meloidogyne incognita*

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Fifty-six rice varieties were screened for resistance to root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne incognita* (Kofoid & White) at Moor Plantation, Ibadan. Plants grown in 10-liter plastic buckets were inoculated with suspensions of RKN eggs and juveniles (5,000/bucket) with 3 replications. Root-galling and nematode recovery were scored 52 d after inoculation.

Faro 21 displayed an exceptionally high resistance (no root galls were recorded) (see table). □

Resistance to RKN at Ibadan, Nigeria.

Variety	Chlorosis index	Gall index ^a	Nematodes (no.)	R factor ^b (Pf/Pi)	Resistance ^c
Faro 1	2	4	15,424	3.08	S
Faro 2	2	4	11,188	2.24	S
Faro 11	1	4	13,606	2.72	S
Faro 19	4	4	10,820	2.16	S
Faro 21	1	3	5,199	1.04	R/S
Faro 27	1	0	5,631	1.13	R
ITA252	1	3	7,548	1.51	HS
M666-301	3	4	8,388	1.58	HS
IR22082-41-2	2	1	6,476	1.30	HS
IRRN29692	1	3	9,945	1.99	S
IR31917-3-1-3-2	1	2	6,658	1.34	HS
IR4744-295-2-3	2	3	3,454	0.69	T
IR18349-22-1-2-1-1	3	3	10,668	2.14	S
IR19672-140-2-3-2-2	3	3	10,448	2.09	S
IR42 (international check)	2	3	6,076	1.22	HS

^a Gall index scale: 0 = 0 galls, 1 = 1-2 galls, 2 = 3-10 galls, 3 = 100+ galls. ^b R factor = average final egg count ÷ 500 (inocula level). ^c R = resistant, T = tolerant, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization TEMPERATURE TOLERANCE

Extent of wind-induced tip drying in popular rice varieties in Coimbatore

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Tip drying due to high wind is common in May-Jun nursery and transplanted crops. Average wind velocities of 30 km/h lead to up to 2 cm drying. Leaves formed without high winds are normal.

We assessed tip drying in pre-release and popular short-duration rice

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